

Pedagogical strategies for enhancing physical activity: A systematic review of trends and approaches

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Abstract

Background and Study Aim

In modern society, issues of physical health and an active lifestyle are becoming increasingly relevant. However, despite the growing interest in this topic, there is a need for a more in-depth understanding of the pedagogical aspects of physical activity. The purpose of this study is to analyze academic publications on the pedagogical aspects of physical activity to identify current trends, issues, and prospects in this field.

Material and Methods

The Web of Science database was used as the source of information. Articles published over the last 10 years were extracted. The search was conducted using the keywords “Pedagogy” and “Physical Activity”. As a result of the search, 93 scientific articles were selected. A special algorithm in the Python programming language was developed for analyzing and synthesizing data from the selected articles.

Results

The analysis of the retrieved publications highlighted two major research themes. The theme “Physical Activity and Health” with 5 subgroups emphasizes the importance of physical activity and pedagogical methods in the educational process and public health. The results illustrate the link between physical activity and improved health, cognitive functions, as well as supporting motivation and autonomy among participants. The significance of integrated approaches and personalized strategies aimed at enhancing quality of life and educational effectiveness is also highlighted. Research in the area of “Physical Education and Pedagogy” with 4 subgroups demonstrates approaches that contribute to physical and psychological well-being. Physical literacy remains an important strategy for developing sports skills and for promoting a healthy lifestyle from an early age. It is noted that effective physical education can significantly enhance academic achievements, emphasizing the importance of implementing comprehensive educational programs.

Conclusions

The research results emphasize the importance of integrating physical health improvement strategies into healthcare policies. Attention is focused on the need for health monitoring and improving access to a healthy environment for all segments of the population. Special attention should be given to preventive measures related to lifestyle improvement and increasing physical activity to combat chronic diseases. The studies confirm that to enhance educational and health-preserving outcomes, it is important to promote policies that support the integration of physical activity into the daily academic and extracurricular lives of participants of all age groups.

Keywords:

Introduction

Modern society faces challenges in the area of health and well-being, including insufficient physical activity. This leads to an increase in the prevalence of various health issues and other problems related to poor physical condition and inadequate levels of physical activity. Therefore, pedagogical approaches that focus on enhancing an active lifestyle among various age groups play a vital role in addressing this problem. In this context, it is evident that there is a need to identify key aspects and perspectives on the use of pedagogical approaches to stimulate physical activity.

Research into the role and significance of physical activity, physical education, and pedagogy allows for finding effective solutions to existing problems. In the context of “Physical Activity and Health,” the research focuses on addressing the following issues.

Physical activity and a healthy lifestyle.

Contemporary research confirms the undeniable role of physical activity in maintaining and improving the health of the population. For instance, updated physical activity guidelines recommended in guides for Americans [1] and by global health organizations [2] emphasize the importance of regular exercise. Global studies indicate that insufficient physical activity is a prevalent issue [3, 4, 5]. In addition to preventing diseases [6, 7, 8], physical activity can also serve as therapy [9] and a means to improve

mobility and muscle function in old age [10, 11]. Analyses also indicate a link between physical activity and a reduced risk of depression [12], as well as the interaction between a sedentary lifestyle and cardiovascular health [13].

Cardiovascular diseases.

Cardiovascular diseases continue to be one of the leading causes of mortality and disability worldwide. Regularly updated statistical reports, such as those by the American Heart Association [14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19], highlight the growing global burden of these diseases. Research also identifies major risk factors, including inadequate physical activity [20] and other global risks [21], which contribute to increasing cases of stroke and heart disease in various countries. These findings underscore the importance of preventive measures, including the development of physical activity guidelines for people who have experienced a stroke, which can significantly improve outcomes and reduce the risk of recurrent events.

Obesity and Metabolism.

The issue of obesity is becoming increasingly relevant on a global scale. Reviews indicate that the prevalence of obesity and overweight continues to rise in most regions of the world [22], correlating with the spread of metabolic syndrome [23]. Detailed epidemiological data point to a range of factors influencing the development of obesity [24, 25]. Additionally, genetic aspects play a significant role in regulating body mass and fat tissue metabolism [26]. Scholarly reviews on childhood obesity discuss its epidemiology, etiology, and consequences [27]. An important aspect of combating obesity is the development and implementation of guidelines for managing adult obesity at the European level [28].

Public Health and Diseases.

Urban green spaces play a crucial role in providing public health and environmental justice. Research highlights the importance of urban green areas in improving the quality of life for city dwellers and reducing environmental injustice [29]. A comprehensive review of systematic studies shows how urban greenery affects public health outcomes, including reducing the incidence of various ailments [30]. Additionally, recent data on the epidemiology of Parkinson's disease [31] and atherosclerosis [32] identify potential links between access to green areas and reduced risks of developing these diseases, emphasizing the significance of environmental factors in disease prevention and population health management.

Oncology.

Cancer remains one of the leading causes of mortality worldwide, as confirmed by studies examining its prevalence, mortality, and the loss of potential life years [33]. Significant attention

is given to the development and optimization of dietary and physical activity recommendations for cancer patients, aiming to enhance their survival and quality of life [34, 35]. Common risk factors for cardiovascular diseases and cancer are studied intensely, highlighting their interconnection [36]. Research further focuses on the impact of body mass index on the survival of women with breast cancer [37].

Diverse Approaches in Health and Physical Activity.

Modern guidelines for the prevention of cardiovascular diseases emphasize the importance of regular physical activity and its role in improving health and reducing disease risk [38, 39]. Studies on the impact of a sedentary lifestyle demonstrate its association with an increased risk of chronic conditions [40, 41, 42] and highlight the importance of monitoring physical activity levels [43, 44]. The positive effects of high-intensity interval training on individuals with lifestyle-related disorders are also noted [45]. These findings reinforce the need for integrating physical education programs and exercise into daily life as part of a global strategy to improve public health.

The studies reviewed in the subgroups note that improving physical activity helps reduce the risks of cardiovascular and oncological diseases and plays a key role in combating obesity and metabolic disorders. The research highlights the connection between regular physical exercise and improved overall health, confirming the necessity of integrating an active lifestyle into daily practice and public health strategies. These results demonstrate the potential of various approaches to physical activity in disease prevention and in promoting a healthy lifestyle among different population groups.

In the context of "Physical Education and Pedagogy," research focuses on addressing the following issues:

Motivation and Self-Determination.

Modern research in the fields of pedagogy and physical education emphasizes the importance of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation in the educational process, based on self-determination theory. These studies show how intrinsic and extrinsic motivations interact, affecting academic achievements [46, 47, 48] and student motivation in physical education [49, 50]. The importance of student autonomy and teacher support is demonstrated through its impact on educational motivation and academic outcomes, as well as its connection with teacher burnout [51, 52]. Research also discusses cultural aspects of motivation and learning [53], the development of methods to enhance motivation through personal significance and self-actualization [54], and the relationships with other motivational theories [55, 56]. This field continues to evolve, affirming

the significance of motivational processes in educational activities.

Physical Education and Academic Achievements.

Physical activity significantly affects cognitive functions and academic performance in children and adolescents. Numerous studies indicate that active participation in physical education correlates with improved mental abilities and school achievements [57, 58, 59, 60, 61]. Particular attention is paid to the impact of physical activity on reducing depression levels [62] and increasing physical literacy, which contributes to improved health [63, 64]. The environment, including school [65, 66] and home settings during quarantine [67], plays a crucial role in influencing physical activity levels. Research also highlights the positive effects of mentally stimulating physical activity on executive functions [68, 69] and notes trends in activity and sedentary lifestyles in the USA [70].

Physical Literacy and Educational Strategies.

Physical literacy is a key element in promoting public health and the effectiveness of educational programs. Assorted studies discuss the definitions, foundations, and associations of physical literacy, highlighting its significance and the need for further exploration [71, 72]. Recommendations for physical activity that support public health priorities are crucial for shaping policy and practice in this area [73]. Additionally, in the context of educational processes, research on internet self-efficacy and self-regulated learning shows how interaction and access to information can enhance learnability and motivation [74]. The societal implications and structural biases related to weight, which underscore the importance of an inclusive approach in education and healthcare, are also discussed [75].

Autonomy and Support in Pedagogy and Physical Education.

Contemporary research in the fields of pedagogy and physical education highlights the importance of autonomy and support in the learning process, which contribute to higher levels of engagement and motivation among participants. Studies show how supporting autonomy can enhance the perception of the educational process and reduce burnout among teachers [76, 77, 78]. The importance of competent teaching in physical education is a main point emphasized through the analysis of models that promote better understanding and practice in this area [79, 80]. Research also points to gender differences in physical activity, underscoring the need for individualized approaches [81]. Additionally, another study demonstrates the positive impact of moderate to intense physical activity on cognitive functions in adolescents [82].

The research reviewed in the subgroups emphasizes the study of approaches to motivation

and self-determination, revealing their key role in improving academic achievements and strengthening students' confidence. In the context of online education, studies highlight the importance of self-regulated learning to enhance student engagement and effectiveness. Physical literacy is a foundation for developing vital skills that contribute to improving public health and preventing diseases. Attention is also focused on the need to create a supportive educational environment that fosters the development of self-management skills and responsibility among students. Together, these subgroups illustrate the multifaceted impact of physical education on forming a healthy and educated society.

Analysis of the studies has revealed significant interest in the pedagogical aspects of physical activity and their impact on educational processes. However, despite the extensive body of research, there are still significant gaps and unresolved issues in this area.

The purpose of this review is to analyze academic publications on the pedagogical aspects of physical activity to identify current trends, challenges, and prospects in this field.

Methodology

Information sources

The authoritative Web of Science database was used as the information source.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

The following criteria were established for inclusion in the review: articles must discuss the relationship between pedagogy and physical activity, be published in the last 10 years (2014-2024) and have full texts freely accessible. Articles must be highly cited and rank within the top 100 in the considered category. Articles without an English abstract were excluded. Additional exclusions were made based on specific criteria not listed here.

Search Strategy

The search query was designed to identify articles published in the last 10 years in the Web of Science (WoS) database, using the keywords "Pedagogy" and "Physical Activity." As a result of the search, 503 scientific articles were selected. A special algorithm was developed in the Python programming language to analyze and synthesize data from the selected articles. This algorithm processed the texts of titles, abstracts, and keywords of each article to identify the ten most frequently occurring terms. Based on data analysis, the keywords were divided into two groups according to their relevance to the research topic:

Group 1. Physical Activity and Health. This group is characterized by the terms "physical activity" or "Physical activity."

Group 2. Physical Education and Pedagogy. This group is characterized by the terms “physical education,” “Physical education,” or “Physical Education.”

For further refinement, a search was conducted using these keywords, accounting for case sensitivity, during which data about the 100 most cited articles for each of the two groups were extracted. To preserve the selected 100 documents (articles), the following procedure was used:

1. Data Export: The extracted records were exported in the form of a plain text file. This was done using the Export option in the Web of Science interface, where the file format was specified.
2. Setting the Record Content: During the export of data, the Custom selection feature was used, which allows for precise determination of which data fields need to be saved. For this research, the following fields were selected:
 - Article title;
 - Authors;
 - Annotation;
 - Keywords;
 - Year of publication;
 - Source [journal];
 - Citations.

The content of each article in the saved file was a list of lines enclosed between the elements “PT J” - the first line of data, and “ER” - the last line of data. The most significant lines for analysis began with the following elements:

- AU - authors;
- TI - source title;
- SO - journal title;
- DE - keywords;
- AB - abstract;
- TC - number of citations;
- PY - year of publication;
- VL - volume;
- IS - number;
- BP - starting page number;
- EP - end page number;
- DI - doi;
- UT - article identifier.

At the next stage, the articles were categorized into several characteristic groups.

Group 1 – ‘Physical Activity and Health’ was divided into the following subgroups:

- a) Physical Activity and Healthy Lifestyle;
- b) Cardiovascular Diseases;
- c) Obesity and Metabolism;
- d) Public Health and Diseases;
- e) Oncology;
- f) Diverse Approaches in Health and Physical Activity.

Group 2 – ‘Physical Education and Pedagogy’ was divided into the following subgroups:

- a) Motivation and Self-Determination;

- b) Physical Education and Academic Achievements;

- c) Online Education and Self-Regulated Learning;

- d) Physical Literacy and Skill Development;

- e) Public Health and Disease Prevention;

- f) Autonomy and Support in Pedagogy and Physical Education.

Additional exclusions.

At the final stage of article selection, studies that initially met the inclusion criteria were excluded from the results. This includes oncological research, where the medical theme predominated. Documents involving animal experiments were also excluded, as well as publications of a medical nature. Although these publications mentioned pedagogical aspects and physical activity, they did not present specific research data relevant to the theme of this review. Furthermore, documents were excluded if they advocated the use of physical exercises without necessary justifications or evidence. As a result, 93 publications were selected for inclusion in the review.

Text Processing Methods for Identifying Key Themes.

For a detailed analysis of the content of the articles, a specialized Python script was developed to extract the most frequently occurring words from the abstracts, titles, and the “Keywords” line. This analytical process began with the tokenization of the text of each abstract and title, during which the text was broken down into separate words or phrases. After this, stop words were removed from the text—words that do not carry significant information (for example, prepositions, conjunctions, and pronouns).

The FreqDist class from the NLTK (Natural Language Toolkit) library was used to count word frequencies. This class allows identifying which words appear most frequently in the text, which is key to identifying the most relevant themes and terms related to pedagogy and health in the studied articles. Based on the analysis, the top 10 most frequently occurring words were selected, representing the most characteristic and frequently mentioned concepts in this area of research.

Ethical Considerations

All processes related to the analysis of publications adhered to the ethical standards of scientific research. Since the study was based on the analysis of already published data, additional approval from an ethical committee was not required.

Data Analysis

The collected data were analyzed to identify the main themes and trends in research on physical activity and pedagogy. The analysis included categorizing the studies according to key themes, evaluating methodologies and conclusions, and

synthesizing the results according to the identified themes.

Results

The results of the search and selection process are presented in Figure 1.

The analysis of the content of the extracted publications highlighted the following directions:

1. Physical Activity and Health
2. Physical Education and Pedagogy

Publications for each group are distributed into several subgroups.

Physical Activity and Health Subgroups.

Physical Activity [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 10, 11, 12, 83].

Research emphasizes the importance of physical activity for maintaining good health and preventing various diseases. Studies in this field discuss both the global problem of insufficient physical activity and the positive aspects of regular exercise, including improving mobility in the elderly and reducing the risk of depression.

Cardiovascular diseases [14, 18, 19, 20, 21].

Research identifies key risk factors such as inadequate physical activity, which contribute to an increase in cases of heart disease and strokes across various countries. Special attention is given to the importance of preventive measures and the development of physical activity guidelines for people who have experienced a stroke, which can significantly improve outcomes and reduce the risk of recurrent events.

Obesity and Metabolism [22, 23, 24, 25, 27, 28].

Research emphasizes the diversity of factors influencing the development of obesity, which play a significant role in regulating body mass and fat tissue metabolism. Issues related to childhood obesity, including its epidemiology, etiology, and consequences, are also discussed. An important direction in addressing this issue is the development and implementation of guidelines for obesity management.

Public Health and Diseases [29, 30, 31, 32].

Figure 1. Flowchart of the search and selection process for documents from the WoS database

Research emphasizes the role of urban green spaces in promoting public health and environmental justice. Studies also show the impact of green areas on reducing the incidence of various ailments and suggest potential links between access to green zones and decreased risks of developing these diseases.

Diverse Approaches in Health and Physical Activity [38, 39, 40, 41, 43, 44, 45].

This group of studies encompasses various directions, focusing on the prevention of cardiovascular diseases through regular physical activity and its role in improving overall health. Highlighted are studies exploring the connection between a sedentary lifestyle and chronic conditions, and the role of accelerometry in assessing activity. Last, the impact of high-intensity interval training on health is discussed.

Physical Education and Pedagogy Subgroups.

Motivation and Self-Determination [46, 47, 48, 49, 50, 52, 53, 54, 84, 85, 86, 87, 88, 89].

Research emphasizes the importance of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, based on Self-Determination Theory (SDT). They illustrate the interaction between intrinsic and extrinsic motivations in academic achievements and in physical education. The significance of student autonomy and teacher support is highlighted, which affect educational motivation and academic outcomes, as well as teacher burnout. Cultural aspects of motivation and methods for enhancing motivation through personal significance and self-actualization are discussed.

Physical Education and Academic Achievement [54, 57, 58, 59, 60, 61, 62, 63, 65, 67, 68, 69, 70, 71].

Research demonstrates the significant impact of physical activity on cognitive functions and academic performance in children and adolescents. Physical education classes correlate with improvements in mental abilities and school achievements. Special attention is given to reducing levels of depression and enhancing physical literacy through active exercise. The environment, including school and home settings, especially during quarantine, significantly influences the level of activity. The impact of mentally stimulating physical activity on executive functions is also emphasized.

Physical Literacy and Educational Strategies [71, 72, 73, 74, 75].

Research indicates that physical literacy plays a key role in promoting public health and the effectiveness of educational programs. Studies discuss the definitions and fundamentals of physical literacy. In the context of online education, research on self-efficacy and self-regulated learning shows how access to information can enhance learnability and motivation. Discussions on the social consequences and structural biases related

to weight also emphasize the importance of an inclusive approach in education and healthcare.

Autonomy and Support in Pedagogy and Physical Education [76, 77, 78, 79, 80, 82].

Research shows that autonomy support can improve the perception of the educational process and reduce the level of professional burnout among teachers. The importance of competent teaching in physical education is also emphasized through the analysis of models that facilitate better understanding and practice. Studies highlight gender differences in physical activity, underscoring the need for individualized approaches. They also demonstrate the positive impact of moderate to vigorous physical activity on cognitive functions in adolescents.

Discussion

The aim of this study was to analyze academic publications on the pedagogical aspects of physical activity to identify current trends, issues, and prospects in this field. The main findings demonstrated that physical activity has a significant positive impact on the mental and physical health of various if not all age groups [3, 4, 10, 11, 12, 65], and highlighted the importance of approaches that support student autonomy in the educational process [51, 52, 76, 78]. These results confirm the need to integrate physical activity into educational programs and the importance of considering individual and cultural characteristics when developing educational strategies.

Group "Physical Activity and Health".

Research in this group emphasizes the importance of physical activity for improving the mental and physical health of the population, including children and adolescents. Meta-analyses and systematic reviews [30, 40, 42, 43, 49, 57, 65] demonstrate that regular participation in physical activity is associated with a reduced risk of developing chronic diseases such as obesity and cardiovascular diseases. These findings correlate with the results of other studies [14, 15, 22, 23, 28], highlighting physical activity as an integral part of a healthy lifestyle. However, it is important to note limitations related to the heterogeneity of the study samples and the methods of measuring physical activity, which can affect the generalizability of the results [80].

Group "Physical Education and Pedagogy"

Within this group, important aspects of the impact of pedagogical approaches on student motivation and activity have been identified. Research confirms that approaches supporting student autonomy contribute not only to improved motivation [64, 76, 78, 84, 85, 86, 89, 90, 91, 92] but also to overall educational well-being. Implementing methods based on autonomy in educational practice can be an

effective means of enhancing academic motivation and physical activity among students. Nevertheless, there are barriers related to cultural and individual differences that can affect the effectiveness of these approaches [79, 93, 94, 95, 96].

The data obtained from this systematic review emphasizes the significant impact of physical activity on pedagogical practices and educational achievements across various age groups. Based on these findings, a series of practical recommendations can be proposed for educational institutions and organizations on integrating physical activity into curricula to enhance both the physical and psychological well-being of participants. Specifically, the results point to the need for developing comprehensive educational programs that include physical activity to improve academic performance and overall health. In addition to practical changes, the results of the review underscore the need for policy initiatives to support and promote physical activity within the educational environment. Finally, the data identified highlight key directions for future research, including a deeper exploration of the impact of various types of physical activity on specific academic and psychological outcomes, as well as the development of methodologies for assessing and monitoring the effectiveness of implemented programs.

Limitations

Despite the systematic approach to locating studies, limitations exist at both methodological level and with the located studies. First, it should be noted that though the source of data, that is the located studies, was the Web of Science database. Though this database is viewed across the research community as influential, it could have limited access to relevant studies published in other databases. The importance of articles should not be diminished based on the journal being within the Web of Science database. Even so, choices must be made for the article search methodology. The

lack of inclusion of languages other than English is a limitation. During the selection and analysis of literature on the pedagogical aspects of physical activity, there may have been limitations that could have affected the objectivity and completeness of the results obtained. Additionally, the use of strict keywords “Pedagogy” and “Physical Activity” might have excluded articles related to adjacent topics but classified under different terms. These factors could have led to an incomplete representation of the current state of research in this area, which should be considered when interpreting the results of our study. Last, concerning the included studies, nearly all studies are limited in scope. Hence, even with our included articles, limitations exist in their scope and data presentation.

Conclusions

Despite limitations from methodology and limitations inherent within the gathered studies, the results indicated that regular physical activity promotes improved physical health and positively affects the mental well-being and academic performance of participants. Particularly significant is the impact of physical activity in reducing symptoms of depression and enhancing cognitive functions. However, certain issues were also identified, such as the insufficient integration of physical activity into educational programs and uneven distribution of access to physical education resources, which can exacerbate social inequalities. This highlights the need for developing targeted strategies to improve the accessibility and quality of physical education at all educational levels. The studies reviewed in our analysis confirm that to improve educational and health-preserving outcomes, it is crucial to promote policies that support the integration of physical activity into the daily academic and extracurricular lives of participants of all age groups.

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